

Task Driven Online Impedance Modulation

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Abstract—The effective use of robotics in realistic environments requires robots capable of adapting to different task requirements and in terms of motion tracking performance, interaction forces, payload conditions as well as in uncertainties that may occur during the task execution. While impedance control represents an effective control tool to adapt to the different requirements and uncertainties, the online modulation of impedance during the task execution represents a critical prerequisite, yet it remains an open research topic today. In this work, we present a new method, which permits a robot to modulate online the parameters of its impedance taking into account of the requirements of the task to be performed. The method considers the motion tracking performance requested by the task as well as the expected task payload or interaction forces to derive the stiffness parameter that can ensure the desired performance under the required motion and payload conditions. Appropriate damping levels are also derived to ensure the stability of the modulated impedance on the robot. The method is successfully verified on the CENTAURO robot while performing a number of manipulation tasks with different motion requirements, payload, and interaction settings, showing its function in modulating online the impedance parameters of the robot for ensuring the requested performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

With robotics entering a new era in applications domains involving realistic workspaces, providing effective adaptability to heterogeneous uncertainties is become a fundamental requirement for success in performing different tasks. Impedance control that can allow online to modulate the robot impedance represents a promising tool for enabling robots to compliantly behave and adapt with different tasks requirements as well as unexpected uncertainties that may occur during the execution of the tasks. In particular, since its introduction [1], impedance control has extensively demonstrated its performance in facilitating the robot in performing interaction tasks, [2], [3], [4] when applied in assistive or collaborative robots of various forms, ranging from robotic arms to complex humanoids, and legged platforms, [5], [6]. By properly selecting the inertia, damping, and stiffness parameters, the physical interaction can be tackled in a much more flexible and effective way, when compared to position or force control schemes. An example is shown in [7]. However, the selection of impedance parameters, as well as their online modulation still remains an open research topic in the field.

Such online modulation in the impedance parameters of the robot can simplify the achievement of task performance

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Fig. 1. A drilling task example, showing the trajectory path of the tool with defined varying tracking error margins along the trajectory and the expected payload and task interaction forces during the task execution.

requirements defined in terms of motion precision, interaction forces and payload settings, while remaining compliant as much as possible. The adaptability to uncertainties and the reducing risk of damages or injuries in the case of accidental contacts is remarkably enhanced. To derive such impedance modulation principles, approaches based on biological findings, empirical methods or learning techniques have been explored during the years.

First studies in biological systems, for impedance modulation, [8], [9], reveal humans regulate their arm impedance in a task-oriented manner. Through the co-activation of agonist-antagonist muscles and postural modulation of their arms, humans naturally size and orient the stiffness ellipsoid according to the amplitude and direction of the interaction forces as needed by the task.

The work of [10] follows an empirical method to derive the rule of a varying impedance based on the absolute value of the end effector Cartesian velocity. Similarly, [11], [12], and [13] use model-based approaches.

Learning techniques have been also applied to determine the impedance parameters. An exhaustive survey on learning methods for variable impedance control can be found in [14]. Typically, the techniques used are mostly the Imitation Learning (IL), Learning from Demonstration (LfD), iterative learning as well and Reinforcement Learning (RL).

Motivated by the above literature, a novel online impedance modulation method that permits a robot to modulate on the fly the parameters of its impedance is proposed in this work. The novelty of the method is on the fact the impedance modulation is directly linked to a number of task requirements that can be explicitly defined and vary during the task execution. The number of task requirements

can specifically include: the motion tracking performance (desired task error), the expected payload, and/or interaction forces needed along the task execution to successfully complete the task. We therefore propose to consider the desired motion tracking error and the desired wrench (which takes into account the payload or the interaction forces) needed to be applied at the end-effector of the robot to execute the task as the primary task performance requirements to generate the varying stiffness and damping profiles for the robot joints in order to ensure the specified task performances. Our motivation for considering the task motion tracking performance and the desired wrench comes from the fact they represent two primary requirements, which can be defined based on the task nature and known information while studies have suggested correlations between joint effort and tracking performance with impedance modulation in the human arm [15], [16]. In addition, by permitting the online variation of the task tracking and force requirements, the method provides the flexibility to eventually impose stricter or more relaxed requirements during the task execution, enabling to modulate the robot impedance at the level needed by the instantaneous required tracking performance and force. This can permit to maintain a more compliant behavior for the phase of the execution for which lower tracking precision is needed by the task, e.g. in the middle of a trajectory during the approaching phase or lower/no payload or interaction forces are needed to be supported or exerted by the robot.

The stability property of the proposed method is also considered during the online modulation of stiffness and damping parameters by adapted the generated profiles to primarily ensure stability and secondarily the task performance to not compromise the entire task execution.

The method is validated through a number of experiments performed with the CENTAURO Robot [17], fig. 1.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the problem statement, Section III reports the details of the impedance modulation method, while Section IV discusses the stability analysis, Section V discusses the experiments performed to validate the method and Section VI addresses the conclusion.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Realistic environments introduce a significant level of uncertainty to the robotic systems. In addition, task variability and unstructured environment settings can make the operation of robots in these workspace conditions extremely challenging. Consider, as an example, a drill task performed by a robot. Such a task may request different motion performance e.g. lower motion accuracy during the approaching phase of the trajectory and higher when arriving at the goal location to locate the drill against the wall plane. fig. 1. During the execution, the achieved task performance may also be affected by the uncertainty of the payload level or interaction forces experienced due to imprecise wall location as well as due to the drilling operation itself. The execution of such a task would therefore require adaptability by the robot to ensure the performance. In conclusion, impedance

modulation could enable to address this challenge by varying the robot impedance in consideration of a set of requirements for the task in terms of desired task error and desired wrench, permitting to adapt, accordingly, the impedance parameters with these requirements.

III. ONLINE IMPEDANCE MODULATION DESIGN

In this Section, the proposed impedance modulation method is introduced.

A. Preliminaries

A fully actuated articulated robot with n joints can be described by the following model:

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) = \tau + J(q)^T w_{ext} \quad (1)$$

where $q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are joints position, velocity, and acceleration vectors of the robot, $M(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ represents the inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ represents the Coriolis term, $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the gravity vector, $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the joints torque as an input, $J(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times n}$ is the Jacobian matrix which relates the n the robot's velocity and the linear and angular velocity of a frame attached to the robot end-effector, and $w_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the external wrench. In this model, the matrix $C(q, \dot{q})$ can be chosen such that $\dot{M}(q) = C(q, \dot{q}) + C(q, \dot{q})^T$ holds, and having $\dot{M}(q) - 2C(q, \dot{q}) = 0$. It is well known that this property corresponds to the passivity of the system with respect to the input joint torque τ and the output joint velocity \dot{q} .

B. Online Impedance Modulation Principle

The impedance modulation strategy proposed in this work targets to ensure the task performances requirements defined in terms of a desired task error and a desired wrench at the end-effector.

Given the robot model provided in (1), we consider the following proportional-derivative (PD) control law with gravity and external wrench compensation,

$$\tau = K_J(t)(q_d - q) - D_J(t)\dot{q} + \tau_g + \tau_{ext} \quad (2)$$

where $q_d \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the desired joints position vector, $\tau_g \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the gravity torque vector, $\tau_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the torque generated by the external wrench acting on the robot ($\tau_{ext} = J(q)^T w_{ext}$), $K_J(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $D_J(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are the varying joints stiffness and damping matrices.

Let consider now a Cartesian task with requirements of a desired task error $\Delta x_{ee}^{t,d} \in \mathbb{R}^6$, where the orientation part is expressed using Euler's angles, and a desired task wrench $w_{ee}^{t,d} \in \mathbb{R}^6$. In order to accomplish the task and meet the task requirements modulating the impedance of the robot, we impose a virtual spring attached to the robot end-effector and set a desired Cartesian stiffness (chosen diagonal) $K_C^d = \text{diag}\{k_c^d\} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$. The desired Cartesian stiffness is computed as follows

$$K_C^d = \frac{|w_{ee}^d|}{\Delta x_{ee}^d}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the Task Driven Online Impedance Modulation.

where $w_{ee}^d \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the desired wrench and $\Delta x_{ee}^d \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the desired error, both at the end-effector.

The desired wrench is given by a model-based gravity component $w_g \in \mathbb{R}^6$, and an external component $w_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ representing the expected payload or interaction force to be supported and/or applied. The desired task wrench is modeled as an external wrench ($w_{ext} = w_{ee}^{t,d}$). Consequently, the desired wrench is computed as a sum of those terms: $w_{ee}^d = w_g + w_{ext}$.

The desired error can be constant or time-varying along the desired trajectory depending on the accuracy required in the different segments of the motion. Therefore, with the aim of having the robot compliant as much as possible, in this work, we derive the desired error along the robot trajectory using the following formula

$$\Delta x_{ee}^d = d(t) \cdot \Delta x_{ee}^{initial} + (1 - d(t)) \cdot \Delta x_{ee}^{t,d}, \quad (3a)$$

$$d(t) = \frac{d(t)^{actual}}{d^{initial}}. \quad (3b)$$

where $x^{initial} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the initial error (design parameter), $d(t)^{actual} \in \mathbb{R}$ is the distance of the final pose (target) from the actual pose of the end-effector, $d^{initial} \in \mathbb{R}$ is the initial distance of the end-effector from the final pose. The distance follows the 2-norm computation. Thus, $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is a value from 0 to 1. It is 1 at the beginning and goes to 0, when we reach the target. Fixed an initial tracking error and based on the distance from the final pose, the above formula permits to set a larger tracking error along the trajectory during the approaching phase and finally arriving in the goal position with the error demanded by the task (desired task error).

Once computed the desired Cartesian stiffness matrix, the required joint stiffness to realize the desired Cartesian stiffness can be determined as follows [18]

$$K_J(t) = J(q)^T K_C^d J(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (4)$$

with $(\frac{\partial J(q)^T}{\partial q} K_C^d \Delta x_{ee} = 0)$. The varying joint damping is then derived in accordance with the level of the joint stiffness similarly to [19]

$$D_J(t) = 2\xi \sqrt{K_J(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (5)$$

where $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$ is the damping ratio to be defined. The square root is meant as the square root of the diagonal elements. Finally, the joint stiffness and damping matrices computed in (4) and (5) are sent to the robot control as follows. The diagonal elements are directly implemented to the low level robot control, and the *off*-diagonal terms are realized by an appropriate feed-forward torque. Further details of the low level control can be found in [20]. Fig. 2 provides an overview of the proposed task driven online impedance modulation scheme with the stability check explained in details in the following section.

IV. STABILITY ANALYSIS

The impedance modulation during the task execution may introduce implications in the stability of the robot control. The classical approach to prove the stability of an impedance control is based on the Lyapunov candidate function [21]. The work in [22] proposed a stability condition, which is robot state independent. Finally, other works employ an energy tank-based approach to guarantee the stability of the system, preserving its passivity [23].

In this section, we provide a stability analysis of the system provided in (1), (2) with the proposed joint impedance (stiffness and damping) modulation, equations (4) and (5), using the Lyapunov direct method [24]. Subsection introduces the formal stability derivation while Subsection B discusses how the stability of the system during the execution (online check) is ensured.

A. Stability Analysis

For a given q_d , the error vectors, $\bar{q} = q - q_d$, $\dot{\bar{q}} = \dot{q} - \dot{q}_d$ and $\ddot{\bar{q}} = \ddot{q} - \ddot{q}_d$ can be introduced. Assuming that $K_J(t)$ and $D_J(t)$ are time-varying and at least semi-positive definite, we choose the following Lyapunov candidate function

$$V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T M(q) \dot{\bar{q}} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{q}^T K_J(t) \bar{q}, \quad (6)$$

with $V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ positive definite, ($V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) > 0$) to proof the stability of our system. The stability of the system is satisfied if the derivative of the Lyapunov candidate function

is at least semi-negative definite ($\dot{V}(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) \leq 0$). Therefore,

$$\dot{V}(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T \dot{M}(q) \dot{\bar{q}} + \dot{\bar{q}}^T M(q) \ddot{\bar{q}} + \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T \dot{K}_J(t) \bar{q} + \dot{\bar{q}}^T K_J(t) \dot{\bar{q}} \quad (7)$$

From the equations (1) and (2), and by using $\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, \ddot{\bar{q}}$, gives $\ddot{\bar{q}} = M(q)^{-1} \{ -(C(q, \dot{q}) + D_J(t)) \dot{\bar{q}} - K_J(t) \bar{q} \}$ and by substituting it into (7), we obtain

$$\dot{V}(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) = -\dot{\bar{q}}^T D_J(t) \dot{\bar{q}} + \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T \dot{K}_J(t) \bar{q} \leq 0. \quad (8)$$

where we used the system property $\dot{M}(q) - 2C(q, \dot{q}) = 0$. The above (8) establishes the stability condition to guarantee for the system with impedance modulation. The condition is guaranteed if the variation of the derivative of the stiffness is negative, i.e. the derivative of the Lyapunov candidate function is negative definite, otherwise the following condition needs to be satisfied to guarantee the stability of the system

$$\dot{\bar{q}}^T D_J(t) \dot{\bar{q}} \geq \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T \dot{K}_J(t) \bar{q}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, the system has a stable behavior if the dissipative term given by the varying damping term multiplied by the joint velocity error is greater than the variation of the varying stiffness matrix multiplied by the joint position error.

B. Ensuring Stability

In the proposed impedance modulation, the stiffness and damping can not be therefore arbitrarily commanded due to stability consideration as shown above. Thus, to fulfill the stability condition provided in (9), the joint stiffness and damping may need to be adjusted. Using the property of the quadratic form as provided below

$$\lambda_{\min}(A) \|x\|^2 \leq x^T A x \leq \lambda_{\max}(A) \|x\|^2, \quad (10)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is a square matrix with m dimension, $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a vector with the same dimension m , and $\lambda_{\min/\max}(A)$ denotes the minimum and maximum eigenvalue of A , respectively. $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the l_2 -norm, the condition expressed in (9) can be computed as follows

$$\lambda_{\min}(D_J(t)) \|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2 \geq \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{\max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \|\bar{q}\|^2 \quad (11)$$

Therefore, to ensure the stability of the system, the minimum eigenvalue of the joint damping is lower bounded as below

$$\lambda_{\min}(D_J(t)) \geq \lambda_{\min, D_J}^{stable} \quad (12)$$

with $\lambda_{\min, D_J}^{stable} = \lambda_{\max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \frac{\|\bar{q}\|^2}{2\|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2}$. If the computed joint damping as provided in (5) violates this constraint, the joint damping is adjusted as below

$$\bar{D}_J(t) = 2\xi \sqrt{K_J(t)} + \Delta_{D_J} I \quad (13)$$

where $I \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the identity matrix and $\Delta_{D_J} = \lambda_{\min}^{stable} - \lambda_{\min}(D_J(t)) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the minimum value required to modify the computed damping to ensure the stability condition (12). Given a maximum allowable joint damping gain that can be rendered by the local joint controllers, $D_J^{max} =$

$\text{diag}\{d_j^{max}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, only joint damping increment alone may not be adequate to satisfy the stability condition if a higher joint stiffness is requested. In particular, If the required damping increment leads to a quantity of damping greater than the maximum joint damping limit, the joint damping is increased until its maximum value and the stability condition is then ensured by acting on the joint stiffness, decreasing it appropriately or maintaining it fixed. Subsequently, the maximum eigenvalue of stiffness derivative is computed to achieve the stability as shown below

$$\lambda_{\max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \leq \lambda_{\max, K_J}^{stable} \quad (14)$$

with $\lambda_{\max, K_J}^{stable} = \lambda_{\min}(D_J^{max}) \frac{2\|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2}{\|\bar{q}\|^2}$. The joint stiffness $K^{stable}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is therefore determined in order to realize the stiffness derivative of the joint that ensures the stability condition (14). Summarizing, the proposed variable impedance modulation, which also ensures the stability of the system, is determined as follows

$$K_s(t) = \begin{cases} K_J(t) & \text{if (11) or (12) is satisfied} \\ K^{stable}(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Similarly for the damping,

$$D_s(t) = \begin{cases} D_J(t) & \text{if (11) is satisfied} \\ \bar{D}_J(t) & \text{if (12) is satisfied} \\ D^{max} & \text{neither (11) nor (12) is satisfied} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

V. EXPERIMENTS

To demonstrate and validate the proposed impedance modulation method, a set of experiments were performed, involving two tasks, a payload lifting task and a drilling task. In the first task the robot impedance is modulated in accordance with the task requirements, which are the required payload and motion precision. Similarly, the second task has been carried out with the aim to show the impedance modulation in a task involving physical interaction forces during the task execution. The two tasks have been performed on the CENTAURO platform, a quadruped robot with wheels and a human-like torso with two arms

A. Experimental Setup

In this section, the experimental setup of the tasks executed are detailed.

Lifting task: this task involves a lifting motion of a payload (fixed mounted on the robot end-effector) for a certain travel distance along one direction. In particular, a weight payload of 2kg is lifted for a travel distance equal to 0.10m along the z direction. Two executions of the lifting task were performed using different desired task errors ($\Delta x_{ee}^{t,d}$): 0.03m and 0.10m , respectively, to demonstrate how the impedance of the robot is modulated when a more or a less strict tracking error is required. The desired tracking error components along the other directions have been assigned a lower desired tracking error equal to 0.10m with the aim to realize a stiffer behavior along the z direction of the task, and a more compliant one in the other directions that are defined as less important for

this task. The force required to execute the task expressed in terms of external wrench is set equal to $w_{z,ext} = 20N$ to compensate the weight of the attached payload. The setup of the task is shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3. *Lifting Task*: The right arm of the CENTAURO robot is used to lift up the weight of 2kg with different desired task errors: $\Delta x_{z,ee}^{d,lift1} = 0.03m$ and $\Delta x_{z,ee}^{d,lift2} = 0.10m$, and a force set equal to $w_{z,ext} = 20N$ was used to compute the desired wrench at the end-effector. The reference frame is the frame attached to the torso F_{torso} .

Drilling task: This task involves the drilling of a concrete masonry unit. The task has been executed with two different motion velocities. The desired task tracking error along the x direction of the drilling was set equal to $0.03m$ for both, while in the other directions it was set equal to $0.06m$ (y -axis), and $0.04m$ (z -axis). Such tracking error settings are expected to generate a stiffer behavior in the x direction to enable the drilling propagation compared to the stiffness of the other two directions. Similarly the stiffness in the z direction along which the arm of CENTAURO experiences the drill tool gravitational load, will be higher than that of the y direction along which no payload or interaction forces are expected.

The force required to execute the drilling task has been roughly estimated through some trials and set equal to $w_{x,ext} = 200N$ along the x direction of the drilling. The setup of the task is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4. *Drilling Task*: On the right arm of the CENTAURO robot a drill is mounted and task is executed with two different motion velocities. Both trials consider a force set equal to $\Delta x_{x,ee}^{d,drill1} = 200N$ along the x direction of the drilling to compute the desired wrench at the end-effector and a desired task motion tracking error of $\Delta x_{x,ee}^{d,drill1} = \Delta x_{x,ee}^{d,drill2} = 0.03m$. The reference frame is the frame attached to the torso F_{torso} .

The initial error ($x_{ee}^{initial}$) in the robot has been chosen equal to $0.10m$.

The tasks have been performed with a joint damping ratio in (5) $\xi = 0.7$. The reference frame used to express the Cartesian quantities is the frame attached to the torso of the robot, F_{torso} as shown in the figures 3 and 4. The tasks have been executed as follows. The lifting task starts with a transition phase (of a duration of 5s) in which the wrench at the end-effector should be smoothly adjusted at the desired level. During this period, no reference trajectories are sent to the robot arm. The adjustment of the wrench follows a smooth trajectory to prevent a sudden increment of the robot gains leading into a fast and undesired behavior of the robot arm. However, in order to be able to safely mount the payload on the robot arm we needed to already set the impedance at the level required to maintain the load. After that, the robot arm starts to move from the starting pose to the final pose, while the impedance is modulated as detailed in sections III and IV. The time chosen to reach the final pose has been set equal to 10s.

The drilling task immediately starts to move the drill tool towards the x direction of the drilling. An end-effector force estimation module, which utilizes the joint torque measurements on the robot arm, is used to detect the contact of the drill bit with the concrete block. At the time, when the contact is detected, a transition phase starts during which the robot motion stops at the pose in which the contact was detected while the wrench at end-effector is smoothly increased to the level desired and specified by the drilling task. Once, this phase is finished, the robot continues to move towards the x direction of the drilling that is normal to the plane of the concrete block unit, while the impedance is modulated as described in sections III and IV. Two drilling trials were performed at different motion velocities. The stability condition of the system is evaluated online during the full execution of the task as explained in section IV-B.

B. Experimental Results

The results from the two tasks performed are discussed in the next paragraphs.

Lifting task: To present the results obtained with our impedance modulation method aimed to satisfied the task requirements (desired task tracking error and desired payload wrench), we execute the lifting task with two different desired task tracking errors. Including the payload compensation in the external wrench to compute the desired wrench at the end-effector, the desired Cartesian stiffness obtained is shown in the figure 5 (top-right). As we can see, a lower desired task error, in the direction of the task (z), results in a higher desired Cartesian stiffness along this direction to be realized by the robot. In particular, the increment of the desired Cartesian stiffness is time-varying, maintaining the robot compliant as much as possible while making the robot stiffer when we reach the final pose. Therefore, the level of the desired Cartesian stiffness is lower at the beginning of the motion and higher when we reach the final pose. The robot impedance (both joint stiffness and damping) needed

Fig. 5. Lifting Task: the results of the experiments executed for the impedance modulation for the lifting task are shown in the above plots. The plots show a comparison between the execution of the task with two different desired task errors (green and blue lines), and the different impedance modulations (of the robot arm, 7DOFs) as a result of the different task motion tracking requirements. The bold dashed red line denotes the start of the task. The execution of the task starts with a transition phase (denoted with the light red area). Top-Left: Trajectory Error (measured and planned), Top-Right: Desired Cartesian Stiffness (planned), Bottom-Left: Joints Stiffness (planned), Bottom-Right: Joints Damping (planned).

to execute the task increases in accordance with it, figure 5 bottom-left and bottom-right plots, respectively. In detail, the joints more involved in the task execution (first three joints of the robot arm) experience a larger increase of the robot impedance (stiffness and damping) with respect to the other joints. The trajectory errors are shown in the top-left plots in figure 5, satisfying the task requirements (in terms of desired task error) in both cases: $0.03m$ and $0.10 m$.

Drilling task: To present the results obtained with our impedance modulation method when interaction forces are present during the execution of the task, we perform two

drilling task trials with different trajectory velocities while the desired task error and desired wrench at the end-effector were kept the same for both trials.

In the plots in figure 6, the contact detection is highlighted with the blue and light blue bold dashed lines for the two drilling experiment trials. Due to the different velocity of the trajectory in the two experiments, the contact is detected at different times. The contact detection occurs when the force estimated at the end-effector is greater than a fixed threshold. In these experiments, the force threshold for the contact detection was set equal to $25N$ chosen by

Fig. 6. Drilling Task: the results of the experiments executed for the impedance modulation for the drilling task are shown in the above plots. The plots show a comparison between the execution of the task with two different execution time, 5s and 10s, respectively. The bold dashed red line denotes the start of the task. The execution of the drilling task itself starts at the moment of the contact detected represented with the bold dashed lines colored with light blue and blue denoting the two different task executions. At the moment of the contact detection, a transition phase starts and finishes after 5s (denoted with the thin dashed lines with colors light blue and blue) where the force at the end-effector is increased at the level demanded by the task. Top-Left: Trajectory Error (measured and planned), Top-Right(in order): Desired Cartesian Stiffness (planned) and Estimated Force (measured), Bottom-Left: Joints stiffness (planned), Bottom-Right: Joints Damping (planned).

trials. When the contact is detected, the wrench at the end-effector is smoothly adjusted to the desired wrench. The desired Cartesian stiffness increases in accordance with the increment of the desired wrench and due to the varying desired task error equation 3a during the drilling phase. The planned variations are present only along the x direction of the task. Consequently, the robot maintains more compliant settings along the y and z directions. The modulation of the robot joint stiffness and damping follows the same trend, starting changing at the moment of the contact detection and increasing accordingly to realize the desired Cartesian stiffness. It can be seen in the plots in fig. 6 (bottom) that

the joints showing higher modulation in their impedance parameters are those mainly contributing to the motion and wrench generation during the execution of the drilling task. Due to the posture of the arm (the forearm is almost straight long the x direction of the drilling motion), these joints are the first three joints of the robot arm. In both trials the tracking error remains, fig. 6 (top-left), within the desired task error of $0.03m$ set by the task requirements. Looking on the estimated forces, fig. 6 (top-right), it can be observed they display higher levels than the desired force level of $200N$ set in the task wrench requirements. This can be explained from the fact the desired contact force is rendered

in an open loop manner through the feed forward torque component in (2). Given a desired drilling trajectory, higher contact forces will be generated if the motion propagation of the drilling is actually slower than the desired drilling motion trajectory sent to the robot. Therefore, drilling motion trajectories of higher velocity will result in a higher tracking error and thus higher contact forces than the desired ones. This is confirmed by looking at the tracking error and contact forces of the higher-velocity trial (light-blue lines) that are higher compared to those of the lower velocity (blue lines) execution. In the plots, only the three translation components are shown since they are the main interested by the task. For the rotational components, we set a level of accuracy at the Cartesian level equal to 0.1 rad with which we have executed the experiments.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented a novel online impedance modulation for the robot joints aimed to satisfy desired task motion tracking error and desired wrench at the end-effector. We derive the online varying Cartesian stiffness to be realized by the robot while online ensuring the system stability using the Lyapunov direct method. Finally, the proposed impedance modulation was implemented on the CENTAURO robot and experimentally verified.

Future work will concentrate on extending the presented impedance modulation method by incorporating a feedback correction action on the desired impedance. This is expected to increase the robustness of the method, specifically to uncertainty adaptation. Furthermore, the case of redundant robots can be investigated and the effect of the presence of a null-space analyzed. Finally, tracking performance will be also modulated according to the presence or proximity of the human operator for safety considerations, e.g. by relaxing the tracking error performance and making the robot behaviour more compliant in the case of human presence in the robot vicinity.

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